

Assessing the suitability of the minimum capture size and protection regimes in the gooseneck barnacle shellfishery

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Minimum capture size

High variability of Total Length (TL) respect to Rostro-Tergum length (RT)

Estimation of an alternative Catch-Size (RT)
26 mm (RT)

Protection regimes

MDS analysis

NO EFFECT of Seasonal Closure under the TL catch-size

Seasonal closure may lead to the population recovery after the fishery season

Application of a suitable catch-size

1 **Assessing the suitability of the minimum capture size and protection regimes in the**
2 **gooseneck barnacle shellfishery**

3

4 **Abstract**

5

6 The suitability of a total-length-based, minimum capture-size and different protection regimes
7 was investigated for the gooseneck barnacle *Pollicipes pollicipes* shellfishery in N Spain. For
8 this analysis, individuals that were collected from 10 sites under different fishery protection
9 regimes (permanently open, seasonally closed, and permanently closed) were used. First, we
10 applied a non-parametric regression model to explore the relationship between the capitulum
11 Rostro-Tergum (RT) size and the Total Length (TL). Important heteroskedastic disturbances
12 were detected for this relationship, demonstrating a high variability of TL with respect to RT.
13 This result substantiates the unsuitability of a TL-based minimum size by means of a
14 mathematical model. Due to these disturbances, an alternative growth-based minimum capture
15 size of 26.3 mm RT (23 mm RC) was estimated using the first derivative of a Kernel-based non-
16 parametric regression model for the relationship between RT and dry weight. For this purpose,
17 data from the permanently protected area were used to avoid bias due to the fishery. Second, the
18 size-frequency distribution similarity was computed using a MDS analysis for the studied sites
19 to evaluate the effectiveness of the protection regimes. The results of this analysis indicated a
20 positive effect of the permanent protection, while the effect of the seasonal closure was not
21 detected. This result needs to be interpreted with caution because the current harvesting based
22 on a potentially unsuitable minimum capture size may dampen the efficacy of the seasonal
23 protection regime.

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29 **1. Introduction**

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31 The primary geographical distribution area of the gooseneck barnacle *Pollicipes pollicipes*
32 ranges from the northwestern coast of France (Brittany) to the northwestern coast of Africa
33 (Senegal) and the Mediterranean (Algeria) (Cruz and Araujo, 1999; Barnes, 1996). This species
34 constitutes the most economically important shellfishery resource on the intertidal rocky shores
35 of Portugal and Spain (Cunha and Weber, 2001, Sousa et al., 2013). This species is highly
36 prized as food (> 50 Euros Kg⁻¹(Jacinto et al., 2010)) and heavily exploited by professional and
37 recreational fishery. In recent years, this species has attracted increased harvesting pressure due
38 to its high market value (Sousa et al., 2013; Stewart et al., 2014), the decline of other coastal
39 fisheries has urged barnacle exploitation as a supplement to fishing activity (Bald and Borja,
40 2012), and the European economic crisis. In many regions of the Iberian Peninsula, this decline
41 has resulted in the overexploitation of the stocks (Borja et al., 2011, Stewart et al., 2014).

42 Likely, the current passive management model of the resource (i.e., non-take zones and legal
43 minimal size of capture) of the northern regions of Spain (Cantabria, Basque Country) means a
44 progressive decline of the resources (Jamieson et al., 1999; Bald and Borja, 2012).

45

46 However, the assessment of the performance of these management measures is not easy. The
47 fishery capture data are often scarce and lack precise localization information, which leads to
48 not very rigorous estimations of the fishery pressure upon this resource (Sousa et al., 2013). The
49 highest abundances of *P. pollicipes* are located in the lower intertidal zone (Cruz, 2010; Pavón,
50 2003) of significantly energetic shores that are exposed to dominant swells, which are
51 frequently related to high slopes and the presence of caves and crevices (Barnes, 1996; Cruz,
52 2000; et al., 2006; Borja et al, 2006b). Consequently, the poor capture data and the physical
53 factors determining the distribution of the genus *Pollicipes* and explaining the difficulty of
54 sampling (Bernard, 1988; Parada et al., 2012) contribute to the lack of large-scale population

55 assessment studies and adequate evaluations of the performance of the management measures.
56 As an alternative, the territorial use rights for fishing (TURF), i.e., an area-based management
57 program that assigns a specific area to an individual, group or community, has proven to be an
58 effective approach for the small-scale management of *P. pollicipes* fisheries in NW Spain
59 (Molares and Freire, 2003). The TURF programs grant exclusive fishing access to these
60 communities while giving them management responsibilities, including the development of
61 annual management plans and the maintenance of appropriate controls of fishing mortality
62 (Young, 2013).

63

64 Regardless of the management model, the measures that are oriented toward the achievement of
65 a sustainable exploitation of the resources in N Spain commonly include the minimum size of
66 capture, protected areas (e.g., seasonal or permanent closures) and individual quotas (e.g.,
67 Parada et al., 2012; Sousa et al., 2013). In recent years, to react to barnacle population decline in
68 some regions, the establishment of a minimum capture size has received special attention from
69 managers and researchers, particularly regarding the adequacy of the part of the barnacle that is
70 measured. The commonly used capture size in N Spain based on the total length (TL) may be
71 inappropriate because this measure includes both the hard part (capitulum) and the soft part (the
72 peduncle) of the barnacle. The latter has, a priori, an importantly variable typology, with both
73 barnacles with elongated and with smooth peduncles being able to have the same capitulum size
74 (Parada et al., 2012). This finding may lead to heteroskedastic disturbances in the relationship
75 between TL and the capitulum length, i.e., an important variance in TL with respect to the
76 capitulum length as individuals grow in size. This variability in TL depends on environmental
77 factors, such as hydrodynamic patterns, degree of immersion, availability of food and
78 intraspecific competition (Hoffman, 1988, 1989; Page, 1986; Lewis & Chia, 1981).

79

80 Several authors have regionally determined that the rostro-tergum (RT) (Pavon, 2003) or
81 rostrum-carina (RC) (Cruz, 1993) lengths are the best biometrical variables to explain the

82 growth of this species. Consequently, these two measures and others also based on the
83 capitulum have been considered more adequate for the establishment of the minimum size of
84 capture in NW Spain and SW Portugal (Parada et al., 2012; Sousa et al., 2013). Sestelo and
85 Roca-Pardiñas (2011) recently investigated the minimum capture size for this species using a
86 non-parametric model that analyzes the length-weight relationship and its derivatives. This
87 author suggested an RC length-based capture size that ensures the maximum yield in weight
88 from the fishery. To our knowledge, no information has been published on the impact of the
89 change in the minimum capture size from the TL-based measure to a capitulum-based measure.
90 Despite considering the alternative minimum size based on the capitulum length, the assumed
91 lower suitability of the TL measure compared to the RC or RT has not been properly
92 investigated in terms of the variability of the TL with respect to the growth of the species, i.e.,
93 in terms of the heteroskedasticity in TL-RT or TL-RC relationships. However, along the
94 northern coast of Spain (Gulf of Biscay), the minimum capture size is still based on the TL.
95
96 Regarding the effectiveness of closure regimes in enhancing population stocks, Cruz (2000) and
97 Sousa et al. (2013) did not find significant effects on the density between areas with different
98 types of exploitation regimes in SW Portugal. Temporal closures (from May to September) are
99 not the most sustainable measures in N Spain because they may not permit the total recovery
100 of the resource after the capture season (Bald et al., 2006). These authors observed that
101 temporal closures could lead to a reduction of the captures by half compared to other measures.
102 These authors developed a dynamic model that is capable of predicting the response of
103 *Pollicipes pollicipes* populations to different management measures and suggested that the best
104 management actions consisted of establishing permanently closed fishing areas that would act
105 as important sources of larvae nourishing the exploited areas and biannual rotational temporal
106 closures. Borja et al. (2006b) analyzed the effect of permanently protected zones in the density
107 and biomass of gooseneck barnacle in Basque Country (N Spain). These authors found a
108 significantly higher density of individuals and biomass in permanently unexploited zones (~8.0

109 Kg m⁻²) compared to that in unprotected areas (~1.5 Kg m⁻²). The failure of the temporal
110 closures might be in part linked to the current minimum size in N Spain.
111
112 The extraction of *P. pollicipes* in N Spain is regulated by regional-scale management models
113 largely based in a legal capture size of 40 mm of total length and different types of closure
114 regimes. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effectiveness or suitability of these
115 management measures, considering that the failure of the temporal closures may be in part
116 associated with the potential unsuitability of the current minimum size. For this purpose, the
117 coastline of Cantabria (Gulf of Biscay) of 215 km was selected as a case study due to (i) the fact
118 that the management model in this region permits the analysis of three types of protection
119 regimes (i.e., permanently open, seasonally closed, and permanently closed) and (ii) the lack of
120 previous assessments of the efficacy of these management measures. The conditional variance
121 of the total length with respect to the growth was analyzed (i) to properly assess the suitability
122 of the capture size based on a measure including the soft part of the barnacle and, if unsuitable,
123 (ii) to estimate an alternative capture size using a nonparametric regression model for the
124 capitulum length-weight relationship. The results may confirm with a mathematical model the
125 suitability of the capitulum length-based minimum size measures that are already implemented
126 in other regions. The size-frequency distribution similarity between zones with different
127 protection regimes was analyzed to evaluate their effectiveness. The results of this latter
128 analysis were interpreted according to the differences between the original minimum capture
129 size and the alternative size that is proposed in this study.

130

131

132 **2. Material and Methods**

133

134 2.1. Study area

135

136 The total area of study covered 215 km of coast in the Cantabria region (Figure 1). Due to the
137 lack of proper habitat suitability data (i.e., mapping), the suitable habitat of gooseneck barnacle
138 was identified using a compilation of information coming from cartographic data, professional
139 shellfishers and technical personnel of the Regional Fishing Directorate. A total of 10 coastal
140 areas of different lengths covering 60 km of coastline were considered common shellfishing
141 zones. These areas were managed under different protection levels according to their fishery
142 closure regime: (1) Llaranza, Ubiarco, Liencres, Arnia, Diablo and Cerdigo were opened to the
143 fishery throughout the year; (2) Arena, PELLEZO and Oreña were seasonally protected, being
144 closed to the fishery from 1st May to 1st October; and (3) Sonabia was permanently protected
145 and closed to the fishery throughout the year (Figure 1). A sampling site that was representative
146 of the abundance of each fishing zone was selected based on the compiled information from
147 shellfishermen and technical personnel. The criteria for this selection were to have similar
148 accessibility and wave exposure for every site.

149

150 **Figure 1**

151

152 2.2. Sampling and laboratory procedures

153

154 Field surveys were carried out during the spring low tides in June 2005, except at Diablo, which
155 was surveyed in October 2005. At each of the 10 sites, 5 intertidal transects were established
156 along 200-300 m of coastline, except in Cerdigo and Diablo (4 transects) and in Llaranza (3
157 transects). At each transect, three different intertidal levels were studied: higher littoral (H),
158 medium littoral (M) and lower littoral (L). The shallow subtidal zone was not considered
159 because this species is mainly distributed and professionally harvested in the intertidal zone
160 (Borja et al., 2006a). The individuals were collected by scraping the rock surface within 50 ×
161 50-cm sampling units. In the laboratory, several biometric variables were measured: (i) Rostro-
162 tergum length (RT) (Pavón, 2003), also known as the maximal capitulum height (MCH) by

163 Cruz (1993) or the capitulum length by Bernard (1988); (ii) rostro-carina length (RC) following
164 Cruz (1993); and (iii) total length (TL) (Hoffman, 1984) (Figure 2). The dry weight (DW) was
165 obtained by drying organisms at 60 °C for 48 h following Cruz (1993). Encrusting and boring
166 animals, mainly located on the capitulum plates, were removed before weighing.

167

168 **Figure 2**

169

170 2.3. Data analysis

171

172 *2.3.1. Evaluation of the total length–based minimum capture size*

173

174 The suitability of the TL for use as a minimum capture size measure was evaluated by analyzing
175 the conditional variance $\hat{\sigma}^2$ of TL, which includes both the soft part of the peduncle and the
176 hard part of the capitulum, with respect to the capitulum length, using the statistical software
177 environment R (R Development Core Team, 2009). $\hat{\sigma}^2$ values that were larger than 1.5 were
178 considered significant in terms of TL variability with respect to RT. The RT size was selected as
179 the capitulum length measure based on a locality criterion, as it was determined by Pavon
180 (2003) as the best biometrical variable to explain the growth of this species in the neighboring
181 coast of Asturias (N Spain). Cruz (1993) found the RC size to be more adequate for this purpose
182 in SW Portugal. In this study, the RC-RT relationship was also first determined to compare our
183 and other results based on the RT size with studies based on the RC size (Figure 3).

184

185 The analysis of RT-TL relationship was conducted using a random subsample of the whole
186 dataset, including all sites and tidal levels. A Kernel-based non-parametric regression model
187 was used for this analysis. The model equation was of the type

188

$$189 \quad RT = m(TL) + \sigma(TL) \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

190

191 where the error variable ε is independent of the covariate TL with $E(\varepsilon) = 0$ and

192 $Var(\varepsilon) = 1$, $m(TL) = E(RT|TL)$ is the unknown regression function, and $\sigma^2(TL) =$

193 $Var(RT|TL)$ is the conditional variance function representing heteroskedasticity.

194

195 The estimation of the above model is based on the use of local linear kernel smoothers (Wand

196 and Jones, 1995). Let $\{(TL_i, RT_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ be an independent random sample, the kernel estimator

197

$$\hat{m}(tl) = \psi(tl, \{(TL_i, RT_i)\}_{i=1}^n, h)$$

198

199 at a location tl is defined as $\hat{m}(tl) = \hat{\alpha}_0(tl)$, where $\hat{\alpha}_0(tl)$ is the first position of the vector

200 $(\hat{\alpha}_0(tl), \hat{\alpha}_1(tl))$, which is the minimizer of

201

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \{RT_i - \alpha_0(tl) - \alpha_1(tl)(TL_i - tl)\}^2 K_h(TL_i - tl),$$

202

203 where $K_h(\cdot) = K(\cdot/h)/h$, $K(\cdot)$ denotes a kernel function (a symmetric density), and $h > 0$ is

204 the smoothing parameter (or bandwidth). Additionally, the residual sum of square approach was

205 used to estimate the conditional variance as

$$\hat{\sigma}^2(tl) = \psi(tl, \{(TL_i, R_i)\}_{i=1}^n, h_R)$$

206 with $R_i = (RT_i - \hat{m}(TL_i))^2$.

207

208 Finally, to determine the model's adjustment, the coefficient of determination was used, as

209 calculated by means of cross-validation (Stone, 1977). This calculation is

$$R_{cv}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i^{(-i)})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}$$

210 where $\hat{Y}_i^{(-i)}$ indicates the estimates of Y_i leaving out the i -th element of the sample as obtained
211 by fitting the corresponding model and $\bar{Y} = n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i$.

212

213

214

215 2.3.2. Estimation of the minimum size of capture

216

217 The conditional variance ($\hat{\sigma}^2$) analysis of TL with respect to RT showed values of $\hat{\sigma}^2$ that were
218 larger than 1.5 beyond TL=15 mm. This result confirmed the current TL-based measure as
219 unsuitable for setting the minimum size of capture. Consequently, an alternative catch size was
220 estimated based on the growth-based RT length measure. Prior to this estimation, the RT size
221 corresponding to the current minimum size of capture in Cantabria (i.e., TL=40 mm) was
222 estimated using the regression model of the equation (1). This estimation permitted the current
223 TL size in RT to be comparable to the alternative catch size that we estimated as follows.

224

225 For individuals that collected from the permanently protected zone of Sonabia, a minimum
226 capture size was estimated using the methodology of Sestelo and Roca-Pardiñas (2011) by
227 means of the RT-DW length-weight relationship. The fact that the analysis was conducted using
228 data from a permanent protected zone ensured that results were not affected by the fishery
229 pressure.

230

231 The following nonparametric model was applied to study the RT-DW relationship

232

$$233 \quad DW = m^*(RT) + \sigma^*(RT) \varepsilon^* \quad (2)$$

234

235 where m^* is the unknown regression function, σ^{*2} is the conditional variance function, and ε^* is
236 the error independent of the covariate RT. The estimation of this model was obtained
237 analogously to the model in (1).

238

239 The first derivative of m^* was calculated to determine an RT-based new suitable size of capture
240 for this species. The ideal size, named rt_0 , was used as the maximizer of the first derivative of
241 m^* . This point could be define as

242

$$243 \quad rt_0 = \arg \max_{rt} m^{*(1)}(rt). \quad (3)$$

244

245 Beyond this point, the increase in weight per unit of size decreases. Thus, this size ensures that
246 individuals that smaller than this size had not yet attained the maximum yield in weight. See a
247 full description of this methodology in Sestelo and Roca-Pardiñas (2011). This RT-DW
248 relationship was also analyzed using the classic allometric model (Huxley, 1924) only with the
249 purpose of comparing the results of both of the models (see Figure A1 in the Appendix). Note
250 that the first derivative of the allometric model cannot show a maximum due to its continuously
251 increasing nature.

252

253 *2.3.3. Size frequency distributions*

254

255 Size frequency distributions with discrete size classes of 5-mm RT intervals were obtained for
256 each site. The population class distribution was also analyzed at each tidal level for the entire
257 dataset. For the descriptive analyses of recruitment patterns and exploitable stocks, two barnacle
258 sizes were selected: $RT < 5$ mm and $RT > 20$ mm. These sizes were assumed to correspond to the
259 previous year recruiters and to the minimum size of capture that is allowed in Cantabria,
260 respectively. The capture size is 40 mm TL, with an approximately 20-mm RT length according
261 to the value that was obtained in the present study (see Figure 4a).

262

263 2.3.4. Evaluation of the protection regimes

264

265 Using the composition of the size frequency distributions at each site as the input data, a
266 similarity matrix was constructed to perform a multidimensional scaling analysis (MDS) (using
267 Manhattan distances) with PRIMER 6.0 software (Primer-e Ltd, 2006). The results of the
268 ordination analyses were used to identify similarities and differences in the population size
269 structure among sites with different protection levels. Similar sites were then grouped using the
270 results that were provided by a single linkage cluster analysis of the same data. The criterion to
271 evaluate the effectiveness of the different protection levels was the following: the sites that were
272 grouped in the same group of non-protected sites were considered to have an ineffective
273 protection regime, while sites that were grouped in a different group to that of non-protected
274 sites were considered to have an effective protection regime. This type of analysis was
275 previously applied, with similar purposes, in SW Portugal by Cruz et al. (2010) and Sousa et al.
276 (2013) for *P. pollicipes*.

277

278 3. Results

279

280 3.1. Evaluation of the total length–based minimum capture size

281

282 The RT-TL relationship was explained using a Kernel-based nonparametric regression model
283 (Figure 4a). Once the model was applied, it was possible to clearly observe the nonparametric
284 increasing trend of the estimated mean (Figure 4a) and the heteroskedastic disturbances (Figure
285 4b). The conditional variance $\hat{\sigma}^2$ with respect to RT significantly increases beyond a TL size of
286 15 mm (Mean=1.5, CI=(0.9, 1.9)) to display a maximum at TL=58 mm (Mean=4.0, CI=(1.1,
287 5.4)) (Figure 4b). This increase suggests that the TL-based minimum catch-size may not be as a
288 reliable as a capitulum-length growth-based measure. The use of the TL size may lead to (i) not

289 obtaining the maximum yield in weight from the fishery because a great percentage of
290 individuals could correspond to harvestable sizes with an alternative capitulum-based minimum
291 size (see Figure 4a: data with $TL < 40$ mm and $RT > 19.4$ mm) and (ii) harvest individuals clearly
292 smaller than the correspondent capitulum-based minimum size (see Figure 4a: data with $TL > 40$
293 mm and $RT < 19$ mm). Note that $RT = 19.4$ mm was obtained in section 3.2.

294

295 **Figure 4**

296 3.2. Minimum size of capture

297 Based on the nonparametric model that was used to analyze the RT-TL relationship (Figure 4a)
298 and being cautious to interpret the result due to this model's heteroskedastic disturbances, it is
299 possible to suggest a capture size of 19.4 mm (19.0, 19.8) in RT length corresponding to the
300 current 40-mm TL legal capture size. This result needs to be taken with caution due to the
301 observed variability of TL with respect to RT. Using the RC-RT relationship that was obtained
302 in the present study, the corresponding size of the RC was 16.9 (16.8, 17.0) (Figure 3).

303

304 **Figure 5**

305

306 Alternatively and due to the significant heteroskedasticity in the RT-TL relationship, with an
307 increase in the variance as individuals grow in size (Figure 4b), an alternative minimum capture
308 size based on the RT-DW length-weight relationship was estimated. Thus, for individuals that
309 were collected from the permanently protected area of Sonabia, the Kernel-based nonparametric
310 model showed that the regression curve was an increasing function (Figure 5a) that was very
311 similar but displayed some differences in the last part of the curve from that obtained by the
312 allometric model (Figure A1). The first derivative of the initial curve displayed an increasing
313 monotonous function in the first part of the curve and a maximum at a specific size, after which
314 the curve began to decrease (Figure 5b). The size at which the maximum value was obtained for
315 the derivative was 26.3 mm (23.2, 29.1) in RT and was considered the minimum suitable catch

316 size. The RC-RT regression model (Figure 3) was applied to obtain a minimum suitable catch
317 size of 23 mm (22.8, 23.2) in RC length.

318

319

320 3.3. Population size structure

321

322 Size frequency distribution plots for the 10 studied sites and for the three tidal levels are shown
323 in Figure 6. Oreña, Llaranza, Arena and Sonabia stood out appreciably from the rest of the sites
324 with a marked main mode at RT sizes <5 mm. Apart from the <5-mm sizes, the next mode
325 corresponded to the 15-20-mm range in all sites, except for in Prellezo, Diablo and Cerdigo,
326 where the main size mode corresponded to the ranges between 5 and 15 mm, even exceeding
327 the <5 mm range. The relative percentages of individuals of exploitable sizes (>20 mm) were
328 consistently higher at the permanently protected zone of Sonabia (19%). Arnia and Cerdigo,
329 which were opened to the fishery, also showed important percentages of commercial-size
330 individuals (12-15%). The average size structure plots by tidal level (Figure 6b) showed a main
331 mode corresponding to individuals of <5 mm, especially marked at high and medium levels, and
332 a secondary mode in the 15-20-mm range. From that size range onwards, there was a rapid
333 decrease in the commercial sizes (>20 mm), which are mainly concentrated at the medium
334 levels and especially at the lower tidal levels.

335

336 **Figure 6**

337

338 3.4. Evaluation of the protection regimes

339

340 The ordination analysis that was carried out by Multi Dimensional Scaling (MDS) using size
341 frequency distributions showed that the permanently protected site of Sonabia clearly separated
342 from the remainder sites (Figure 7). A Similarity Percentage analysis, SIMPER (Clarke 1993),

343 was performed to compare the size frequency distributions between Sonabia and the rest of the
344 sites and suggested that the main cause of these differences was the higher percentage of large
345 sizes found in Sonabia. The Manhattan distances that were used to group the sites with similar
346 population size structure (16 and 18) grouped 7 sites without showing any distribution pattern
347 that was associated with seasonal closure or non-protection regimes. Cerdigo and Llaranza, both
348 non-protected, were individually grouped apart, being located closer to the 7 grouped sites than
349 to Sonabia.

350

351 **Figure 7**

352

353 **4. Discussion**

354

355 The results of this study suggest that the two most commonly used management measures
356 within the commercial goose barnacle (*Pollicipes pollicipes*) fishery in N Spain, with a
357 minimum capture size of 40 mm TL and seasonally closed areas, are not entirely suitable, at
358 least together, for a sustainable harvesting of the resource. These results are discussed below in
359 the context of the sustainable exploitation of this resource in the studied coast and their
360 transferability to other coastal regions. The result regarding the suitability of temporal closures
361 is interpreted in light of the difference between the current capture size and the alternative size
362 that were proposed in this study. To discuss our results in comparative terms regarding previous
363 studies, a regression model of the relationship between the capitulum RT and RC biometrical
364 measures was formulated. This model shows that RC length was approximately 90% of the RT
365 length (Figure 3), suggesting transforming the data when these measures are compared. The
366 good fit of the model suggests that both of the biometrical variables could be appropriate and
367 easily comparable.

368

369 The peduncle of the barnacle produced heteroskedasticity in the RT-TL relationship, displaying
370 an important variance in TL with respect to the growth-based measure RT as individuals grow
371 in size (Figure 4). This result substantiates with a mathematical model the unsuitability of the
372 TL-based minimum capture size, which constitutes the most common reference measure for the
373 legal minimum size of capture in N Spain, and analytically supports the capitulum measure-
374 based (i.e., growth-based) catch size that is already adopted in several regions of the Iberian
375 Peninsula (Parada et al., 2012; Sousa et al., 2013). Consequently, a new minimum suitable size
376 was estimated following the methodology of Sestelo and Roca-Pardiñas (2011) and based on the
377 RT capitulum length. The first derivative of the nonparametric model showed a suitable
378 minimum capture size of 26.3 mm RT, which corresponds to 23 mm RC using the RT vs RC
379 relationship (Figure 3). The size that was obtained with this methodology ensures the maximum
380 yield in weight from the fishery. This size is clearly larger than the current catch size in N Spain
381 (40 mm TL) considering that the parametric regression model that was obtained in the present
382 study for the RT-TL relationship (Figure 4a) suggested a minimum size of capture of 19.4 mm
383 RT (or 16.9 mm RC) corresponding to the current minimum size of 40 mm TL.

384

385 The results that were obtained in this study agree with the size limit that was recently proposed
386 by Jacinto et al. (2011) in Portugal (50% of the total harvested biomass comprising individuals
387 > 22 mm RC). Sestelo and Roca-Pardiñas (2011) recently investigated the minimum capture
388 size for this species in NW Spain (Galicia) using the same non-parametric model as that applied
389 in this study. Their study, based on RC, estimated a suitable minimum capture size of 21.5 mm,
390 also ensuring that any barnacle under this size has not yet attained its maximum yield in weight.
391 Fishing directorates in different regions of Spain and Portugal have already used the RC length
392 to establish the minimum size of capture. For instance, in Portugal, the capture size is between
393 20 mm and 23 mm in RC length (Sousa et al., 2013), and in Galicia the way to measure the
394 minimum size of capture was changed from the TL (40 mm) to the capitulum-based (CB) length

395 (15 mm) (Parada et al., 2012). Using the CB vs RC regression model of Parada (2013), the
396 minimum capture size for Galicia should be 18.3 mm RC.

397

398 To a greater or lesser extent, these sizes are above the 12.5-mm RC (14.26 mm RT) sexual
399 maturation size (Cruz, 2000) and consequently may permit the production of a minimum of 1-2
400 broods before the designated size is reached (Molares et al., 1994; Pavón, 2003; Sestelo and
401 Roca-Pardiñas, 2011). However, the current minimum capture size in Cantabria (40 mm TL or
402 16.9 mm RC) may be less conservative in terms of the sustainability of the fishery compared to
403 the rest of analyzed capture sizes. The important difference that was observed in the minimum
404 size between the current capture size in N Spain or the capture size that was established in
405 Galicia (18.3 mm RC) and that obtained in our study (23 mm RC) is explained by the highly
406 conservative approach of Sestelo and Roca-Pardiñas (2011). This method to estimate the
407 minimum size of capture not only ensures at least a brood before the designated size is reached
408 but also attains, as discussed, the maximum yield in weight from the fishery. It is also worth
409 mentioning that previous studies estimated the minimum suitable size using individuals from
410 open fishing areas, while our analysis was conducted using data from a permanently protected
411 zone. This analysis ensured that the minimum capture size was estimated using data that were
412 not biased by the fishing pressure. This analysis may also contribute to the slightly larger
413 capture size that was obtained in this study compared to that of Sestelo and Roca-Pardiñas
414 (2011). The transferability of this result to other coastal areas to support regional or zone-based
415 management models could be adequate for the sustainability of the resource in highly exploited
416 areas considering that our result is the most conservative. However, for this purpose, further
417 analysis is suggested, including more data (i.e., monthly data).

418

419 In addition to the methodology that was used and the environmental differences between study
420 areas, the lack of a standardized measure for the RC length could also explain, in part, the
421 differences between the above-described minimum capture sizes. The comparison between the

422 minimum sizes of different studies was performed in terms of the RC length. For this purpose,
423 the given size measure, CB or RT, was transformed to RC using the regression models from
424 Parada et al. (2012: 2013) and that obtained in the present study (Figure 3), respectively.

425 However, the RC length that was measured by Parada et al. (2012, Figure 4) and Sestelo and
426 Roca-Pardiñas (2011, Figure 2) is slightly different from that measured in this study (Figure 2)
427 following Cruz (1993, Figure 2). We chose to measure the RC as did Cruz (1993) because she
428 demonstrated that it was the biometrical measure that best represented the linear growth of *P.*
429 *pollicipes* and is used to establish the minimum capture size in Portugal.

430

431 The permanent protection regime had a positive effect on the population structure in terms of
432 the abundance of large-size individuals (Figure 6). The MDS analysis demonstrated that the
433 permanently protected site of Sonabia clearly separated from the non-protected sites group
434 (Figure 7). This result is in agreement with those of Borja et al. (2006b), who observed that the
435 density and biomass were 5 times higher in permanently unexploited zones than in unprotected
436 areas in the neighboring coast of Basque Country. However, Cruz (2000) and recently Sousa et
437 al. (2013) in a similar analysis did not find any positive significant effect on the percentage of
438 cover or the density of large individuals in no-take areas of central and SW Portugal. Sousa et
439 al. (2013) suggested that the absence of this effect could be observed because the restrictions of
440 exploitation are frequently not respected. However, seasonally protected sites (from May to
441 October) did not show any significant differences in the size frequency distribution patterns
442 compared to those of non-protected sites, i.e., the MDS analysis mainly grouped seasonal
443 closure sites and non-protected sites in the same group (Figure 7). Bald et al. (2006) obtained
444 similar results in the simulations that were conducted to reproduce different closure scenarios
445 using a system dynamic model. These authors considered that 5-7 months of temporal closures
446 are not sufficient to permit a total recovery of the resource after the capture season and
447 suggested an annual alternate exploitation of the fishing zones as the best management decision.

448

449 The descriptive analysis of the size frequency distributions (Figure 5) completed the
450 understanding of the similarities between the sites as observed in the MDS analysis (Figure 6)
451 and confirmed the absence of a positive effect as associated with temporal closures. Sonabia and
452 Cerdigo presented the highest abundance of 20-mm-size individuals and the unique sites that
453 present individuals greater than 25 mm. The case of Sonabia, which was clearly separated from
454 the other sites in the MDS analysis, can be easily explained by the permanent closure of the
455 zone, as mentioned above, while the case of Cerdigo is more probably linked to both of the low
456 coverages that were observed in this coastal zone (Cantabria, 2005), which shows little interest
457 for professional shell-fishermen, and the presence of a high number of deep crevices and a rock
458 islet which are not very accessible to poachers. The analysis of size frequency distribution
459 patterns as conducted by the tidal level showed that larger sizes are found at the lower intertidal
460 level, which is in accordance with previous research in Portugal (Cruz, 2000; Sousa et al., 2013)
461 and N Spain (Pavón, 2003; Borja et al., 2006b). The difficulties that are associated with fishing
462 at the lower tidal levels (Molares and Freire, 2003) might limit the exploitation intensity, and
463 the abundance of large-size barnacles could remain high at this tidal level. Although these
464 results regarding the tidal levels did not contribute to the goals of this study, the observed
465 pattern demonstrates that the population of this coastal region is behaving as do the neighboring
466 zones under fishing pressure.

467

468 At first glance, these results suggest temporal closure as a non-suitable protection regime for
469 assuring the protection and recovery of a population. However, the desirable effect of the
470 temporal closures could be shaded by the fact that fishery is conducted based on a potentially
471 unsuitable catch-size. The results should be interpreted with caution considering that they were
472 obtained under an unsuitable TL-based capture size. The fact that an important percentage of the
473 individuals that extracted using the TL size could be less than a suitable minimum size may lead
474 to important changes in the size-structure of the population and consequently obscure the real
475 effect of the protection in the MDS analysis. The population size distribution would be

476 appreciably different under the alternative capitulum-based minimum size, and in that case, the
477 6-month seasonal closure could have a positive effect, leading to the recovery the population
478 after the capture season. Nevertheless, this seasonal protection regime may not be adequate for
479 highly overexploited populations. A longer fishery closure may be more suitable in these
480 situations requiring a total recovery. Considering the growth rate of this species (Gutiérrez-
481 Cobo, 2012; Cruz et al. 2000) for overexploited areas, a minimum closure period of 2.5 years
482 may be considered, which is the time that is required for goose barnacles to achieve a
483 commercial size in Cantabria.

484

485 **5. Conclusions**

486

487 In summary, the analysis in this paper demonstrated that the minimum capture size based on the
488 growth-based capitulum length measure is more adequate than that based on the TL measure.
489 We suggest a catch size of 23 mm (RC) or 26 mm (RT) in N Spain that is larger than the current
490 catch size that is established in this coast's regions and similar to that proposed in Portugal. The
491 establishment of this size using the first derivative of the length-weight relationship may ensure
492 the maximum yield in weight from the fishery. A seasonal closure of 6 months may not be
493 effective for assuring the total recovery of a highly exploited population after the fishing season,
494 at least if it is not linked to the establishment of a more suitable catch size than the current catch
495 size. Thus, a 6-month seasonal closure should be locally tested in the field under the new
496 minimum size. We also propose a temporal closure of 2.5 years for highly exploited populations
497 to completely recover. Although the analysis applied in this study may be applicable to other
498 coastal areas, the generalizability and transferability of these results to support management
499 decisions at a larger spatial scale are subjected to further research, including monthly data and
500 field experiments, to test the suitability of the obtained results.

501

502

503

504

505 **Appendix**

506 **(Figure A1)**

507

508

509

510

511

512 **Acknowledgements**

513

514 This work was funded by the Fisheries and Agriculture Department of the Regional
515 Government of Cantabria-FADRGC (Spain), and the grants MTM2011-23204 (FEDER support
516 included) of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and 10PXIB300068PR of the
517 Xunta de Galicia. We wish to thank the staff of the FADRGC and the shell-fisherman José
518 Ramón Azcue for the specific support in the fieldwork, the colleagues from IH Cantabria who
519 helped us in the laboratory work, and Nora L. González Villanueva for her detailed drawings of
520 the barnacle.

521

522

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649

650

651 **Figure captions**

652

653 **Figure 1.** Location of sampling sites on the coast of Cantabria (N Spain). * Seasonally protected
654 and ** permanently protected zones. Sites without label represent open fishing zones.

655

656 **Figure 2.** Longitudinal biometric variables measured in *P. pollicipes* following Cruz (1993).
657 RT= Rostrum-Tergum length, RC= Rostrum-Carina length, TL= Total length.

658 **Figure 3.** Relationship between Rostrum-Tergum length (RT) and Rostrum-Carina length (RC)
659 (n=365). Coefficient of determination (R_{cv}^2) calculated by means of cross-validation is
660 presented for the regression model. Confidence intervals (dashed lines) are hardly identifiable
661 due to the good fit of the model.

662

663 **Figure 4.** Regression curve with bootstrap-based 95% confidence intervals (dashed lines) for
664 Total Length (TL) and Rostrum-Tergum length (RT) (n=365) (a) and the conditional variance of
665 TL (b). R_{cv}^2 represents the coefficient of determination for the regression curve calculated by
666 cross-validation.

667

668

669 **Figure 5.** Regression curve (a) and first derivative (b) with bootstrap-based 95% confidence
670 intervals (dashed lines) for dry weight (DW) and Rostrum-Tergum length (RT). Solid vertical
671 line (b) represents the estimated rt_0 or the size at which the derivative has the maximum
672 value. R_{cv}^2 represents the coefficient of determination for the regression curve calculated by
673 cross-validation.

674

675 **Figure 6.** Size frequency distribution plots (% of individuals) of *P. pollicipes*, (a) for each
676 sampling site and (b) for all data at each tidal level. RT: rostro-tergum length.

677

678 **Figure 7.** MDS ordination of the studied sites showing *P. pollicipes* fishery protection levels
679 (Circle: permanently closed fishery; Triangle: seasonally closed fishery; Square: null protection
680 or all year open to the fishery). Manhattan distances are represented by dotted line (distance=16)
681 and solid line (distance=18).

682

683 **Appendix figure captions**

684

685 **Figure A1.** Relationship between Rostro-Tergum length (RT) and Dry Weight (DW) (n=1200).
686 Coefficient of determination (R_{cv}^2) calculated by means of cross-validation is presented for the
687 regression model. Confidence intervals (dashed lines) are hardly identifiable due to the good fit
688 of the model.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6**a)**

Figure 7

2D Stress: 0,06

Protection Level

- ▲ Seasonal
- Permanent
- Non protected

sonabia

cerdigo

arnia

prellezo

diablo

arena

liencres

ubiarco

oreña

llaranza

Figure A1

